

Dunhill Medical Trust

Data management plan required?	Encouraged - The Trust expects all Research Grant holders to publish all findings and make available data generated as a result of the grant with as few restrictions as possible to ensure maximum patient and public benefit, whilst ensuring that appropriate ethical, legal and institutional regulatory permissions are in place in respect of personal data. The Trust acknowledges that intellectual property generated by the grant may however need to be protected for a short period to allow (for instance) an application for a patent to be submitted.'
RDM policy Link	No
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	50% of data storage and archiving up to maximum of £500
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	admin@dunhillmedical.org.uk
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Frequently asked questions for academic and clinical researchers

<https://dunhillmedical.org.uk/faqs-research/>

Grant making policy <https://dunhillmedical.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/18-06-Grant-Making-Policy.pdf>

Accessed: May 2018